

**THE ECOLOGY AND BEHAVIOR OF THE LARGE BROWN FLYING
SQUIRREL (*PETAURISTA PHILIPPENSIS* ELLIOT) IN A RAIN
FOREST FRAGMENT, WESTERN GHATS
(DECEMBER 1999 - APRIL 2000)**

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THE WILDLIFE CONSERVATION SOCIETY**

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ABSTRACT

The feeding habits and nesting behaviour of the large brown flying squirrel *Petaurista philippensis* were studied between December 1999 and March 2000 in a rainforest fragment in the Anamalai Hills, Western Ghats. The flying squirrels were found to feed on ten plant species during the study period. 62.75% of the diet was comprised of the fruit and leaves of *Ficus racemosa*. The fruits of *Ficus racemosa* were the only fruit seen to be consumed but were the most consumed item in the diet (44.66% of observations). Leaves (38.83%), bark (6.8%), flowers (8.73%) and lichen (0.68%) were also seen to be consumed. Flying squirrels were observed nesting on ten occasions. Flying squirrels seemed to prefer nesting in trees of larger girth (avg. $3.35\text{m} \pm 0.226$) ($p = 0.01$). Most nest cavities were located at the height of 18.6m, and most cavities (80%) were natural, formed by heart rot where branches had broken off. The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* was highest along the forest edge (6.11 sightings/km walked) and lowest in the forest interior (3.95 sightings/km walked). Data from 22 spotlighting censuses were used to estimate the density of *Petaurista philippensis* along the edge of the fragment. The density was estimated to be 2.56 squirrels ha^{-1} .

1. INTRODUCTION

Squirrels and Marmots (Mammalia: Rodentia: Sciuidae) are found on most vegetated portions of the earth's surface and have evolved into a wide variety of niches (Thorington and Heaney 1981). There are more than 50 genera, distributed worldwide except for Madagascar and Australia (Nowak 1991). The family is believed to have radiated from the Paleotropics into the New World and is most diverse in South Asia and nearly as diverse in Africa. Nowhere in the Neotropics do the Sciuridae show the variety of forms attained in the Paleotropics (Eisenberg 1981).

The family Sciuridae is represented by both squirrels and marmots (Agarwal 1981), and three adaptations of squirrels are generally seen in this family: the tree squirrels, the ground squirrels and the flying squirrels (Eisenberg 1981). The flying squirrels, subfamily Petauristinae, have evolved into the niche of nocturnal gliders.

Gliding mammals have evolved a skin membrane (the patagium) between the forelimbs and the hindlimbs that extends out when the body is flattened (Eisenberg 1981). This helps them glide considerable distances and is believed to have evolved to enable better exploitation of food resources. Though the patagium facilitates easy movement through trees, it hampers their quadrupedal movements, and they are not as agile as non-gliders when climbing trees (Emmons 1995). As this might expose them to more risk of predation, gliding mammals are believed to have evolved to be nocturnal. There have been various theories explaining the evolution of the gliding habit and the greater diversity and abundance of gliders in the tropics, particularly in Asia.

Gliding mammals in the temperate regions are not strictly arboreal, unlike in the tropics. Emmons (1995) reasons that animals in the north temperate and tropical deciduous forests must come to the ground to forage as there are no year-round canopy resources. Most obligate forest canopy mammals are restricted to evergreen tropical forests where there is no seasonal shortage of canopy resources.

Gliding could have also evolved in response to the features of the habitat. Emmons (1995) later hypothesised that the prevalence of gliding mammals in Asia was due to a lack of a high closed canopy in the evergreen forests. This was based on observations in the dipterocarp forests at Danum, where the emergents are widely separated from other

tree crowns, and the only animals that were seen to cross the non-continuous upper-level canopy from one emergent to another were the gliding or volant mammals.

Of the gliding mammals, flying squirrels are the only mammals to occur through forested areas in three zoogeographic regions (the Palearctic, Oriental and Nearctic). The three other gliding mammalian families – Anamoluridae, Cynocephalidae and Phalangeridae are each restricted to a single zoogeographic subregion (Thorington and Heaney 1981).

Flying squirrels occur in 12 genera and about 36 species, most of which are found in South Asia. From Asia as a center of adaptive radiation, flying squirrels have spread to North America and parts of North Asia and Europe. However, only one genus (*Glaucomys*) in two species is found in North America. *Pteromys volans*, or the Common Flying Squirrel, is distributed across Finland and northern parts of Russia.

In India, the family Sciuridae is represented by 11 genera and 27 species of squirrels and two Palearctic species of marmots. Tree squirrels are represented by 15 species in five genera (*Ratufa*, *Dremomys*, *Callosciurus*, *Funambulus*, *Tamiops*), while flying squirrels are represented by six genera (*Petaurista*, *Eupetaurus*, *Belomys*, *Biswamayopterus*, *Hyloptes* and *Petinomys*) (Agarwal 1981).

Various species of flying squirrels are found in the Himalayas and the North East in India, but only two species of flying squirrels, the Large Brown Flying Squirrel (*Petaurista philippensis*) Elliot and the Small Travancore Flying Squirrel (*Petinomys fuscocapillus*) Jerdon are the only two species of flying squirrels found in south India (Ashraf *et al.* 1993). While *Petaurista philippensis* occurs throughout peninsular India (Prater 1984), *Petinomys fuscocapillus* is an endangered flying squirrel whose distribution is restricted to the Western Ghats and nearby areas (Kurup 1989).

The Large Brown Flying Squirrel (*Petaurista philippensis*) is described as *Petaurista petaurista philippensis* Elliot by Prater (1948) and many of the recent studies (Umapathy and Kumar in press, Ashraf *et al.* 1993) have retained this name. Corbett and Hill (1992), who reviewed the species, have recognized this species as distinct from *Petaurista petaurista* and have assigned it the name *Petaurista philippensis* (Thorington 1993). *Petaurista philippensis* Elliot is considered synonymous with *Pteromys philippensis* Elliot, *Pteromys oral* Tickell and *Pteromys grissiventer* Gray.

The species *Petaurista philippensis* Elliot (1939) is distributed in Sri Lanka, India , north to Bombay and Rajasthan, South Bihar, Burma, Thailand, South China including Hainan and Taiwan and Indonesia (Agarwal and Chakraborty 1979).

In this study, the Large Brown Flying Squirrel will be referred to as *Petaurista philippensis* throughout and all previous accounts/ studies of the species will be referred to by this name. *Petaurista petaurista* is distinct and when used in this study does not refer to the Large Brown Flying Squirrel of the Western Ghats.

The distribution (Agarwal and Chakraborty 1997, Xavier *et al.* 1998), abundance (Ashraf *et al.* 1993, Umapathy and Kumar, in press) and morphometrics (Xavier *et al.* 1998) of the Large Brown Flying Squirrel (*Petaurista philippensis*) have been studied in the Western Ghats, but little is known of the ecology of the species. Its broad distribution and the occurrence of the species in disturbed habitats suggests considerable habitat tolerance. This study aims to fill some gaps in the knowledge of the basic ecology of the Large Brown Flying Squirrel.

THE OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY ARE:

- 1) To determine the diet of the species and the utilization of available food resources.
- 2) To document nesting habits.
- 3) To estimate the density of *Petaurista philippensis* in the study area.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 STUDIES ON FLYING SQUIRRELS IN INDIA

Research on flying squirrels in India has dealt with the description of species (Blandford 1881, Ellerman 1961, Ghose and Saha 1981), taxonomic reviews of species and genera (Ghose and Saha 1981, Wroughton 1911) and records of existing (Lorimer 1924) and new species and subspecies (Saha 1978, Wroughton 1911).

Four genera are restricted to Kashmir and the North East, while only two species in two genera are found in the lower part of the subcontinent (Kurup 1981). As mentioned earlier, the Large Brown Flying Squirrel *Petaurista philippensis* Elliot (1839) and the Small Travancore Flying Squirrel *Petinomys fuscocapillus* Jerdon (1847) are the only gliding mammals of the Western ghats (Ashraf *et al.* 1993). While *Petaurista philippensis* occurs throughout peninsular India (Prater 1948), *Petinomys fuscocapillus* is an endangered flying squirrel whose distribution is restricted to the Western Ghats and nearby areas. This is the only species of the genus that is found in India, the rest being far eastern in distribution (Kurup 1981). Described by Jerdon in 1847, *Petinomys fuscocapillus* has been collected only three times, once recently by Kurup (1989).

Ghose and Chakraborty (1983) reviewed the status of six species of flying squirrels in Darjeeling and Sikkim. They reported a decline in population sizes due to habitat destruction and the illegal trade of flying squirrel pelts.

The Woolly Flying Squirrel (*Eupetaurus cinereus*), which was earlier recorded only in Kashmir and Tibet, was described in northern Sikkim (Agarwal and Chakraborty 1970) and in areas east of northern Pakistan (Zahler 1996).

Ashraf *et al.* (1993) examined the relative abundance of the sympatric flying squirrels *Petaurista philippensis* (Elliot 1839) and *Petinomys fuscocapillus* in the different vegetation types of the Western Ghats. It was found that *P. philippensis* was more abundant in deciduous forests and cardamom plantations of than evergreen forests and that it was low or absent in teak and tea and coffee plantations. Ashraf *et al.* (1993) sighted *P. fuscocapillus* in the evergreen forests of the Anamalais and their study suggested that the species is not as rare as was believed to be. Umapathy and Kumar (in press) studied the occurrence of arboreal mammals in the rainforest fragments in the

Anamalai hills in relation to landscape and habitat parameters. It was reported that the densities of flying squirrels increased with decreasing area and increasing disturbance levels.

2.2 STUDIES ON FLYING SQUIRRELS IN SOUTH ASIA

Kawamichi (1997) examined the relationship between the seasonal availability of food and the timing of bimodal reproduction in *Petaurista luecogenys*. The seasons of highest food availability coincided with the periods of lactation, and the period of lowest food availability was found to coincide with pregnancy. Reproductive characteristics of the red giant flying squirrel *Petaurista petaurista* were studied in Taiwan. Adult females tended to be heavier than adult males, but there were no other differences in body characteristics. Reproduction in this genus occurs twice a year (Kawamichi 1997). *P. petaurista* is a seasonal breeder with low reproductive rates that may be the result of a low predation rate combined with a high degree of folivory.

Feeding behaviour (Ando *et al.* 1985, Funakoshi and Shiraishi 1985) and food habits (Ando *et al.* 1985) of the Japanese Flying Squirrel have been investigated, as well as other aspects of its ecology and behaviour (Baba *et al.* 1982).

2.3 STUDIES ON FLYING SQUIRRELS IN THE TEMPERATE REGIONS

Flying squirrels have been extensively studied in the temperate regions. Many of the studies on the Northern Flying Squirrels were carried out as they are the dominant prey of the Northern Spotted Owls (Carey *et al.* 1992, Rosenberg *et al.* 1993, Zabel *et al.* 1996). Many of the studies on the Southern Flying Squirrel were initiated as they are the competitors for the cavities of the endangered Red-Cockaded Woodpecker (Conner *et al.* 1996, Schaeffer and Saenz 1998, Mitchell *et al.* 1999).

The highest densities of Northern Flying Squirrel (*Glaucomys sabrinus*) were found in old-growth stands. Rosenberg *et al.* (1996) have hypothesised that no or few flying squirrels are likely to be found in clear cuts. Studies by Waters and Zabel (1995), Carey (1992), and Rosenberg and Anthony (1992) suggest a trend of slightly higher densities of Northern Flying Squirrel (*Glaucomys volans*) with increasing stand age.

Density estimates were found to be six times higher in old-growth forest stands compared to young stands (Witt 1992).

The problems of edge effect were found to be especially important when comparisons were made between habitat types like old growth and second growth. Density differences for the Northern Flying Squirrel were studied along a montane successional gradient in the Utah Mountain Meadows and the number of squirrels was highest in *Abies* dominated forest (1.2-5.8 squirrels/ha) (Anderson *et al.* 1980). Taulman *et al.* (1998) investigated the responses of populations of Southern Flying Squirrels to a range of experimental even-aged and uneven-aged timber practices along a gradient of increasing disturbance intensity. It was found that the retention of greenbelts and the presence of mature forest adjacent to logged forests reduced the severity of effects on *Glaucomys volans*.

It was found that in British Columbia, Canada the populations of the Northern Flying Squirrels were limited by availability of food. Stands with experimental food supplementation had higher densities of flying squirrels (1.38/ha and 1.5/ha) than old-growth forest control sites (0.64/ha and 0.68/ha) (Ransome and Sullivan 1997). Waters and Zabel (1995) explained the difference in density of flying squirrels *Glaucomys sabrinus* between old growth and second growth stands by the availability of hypogeous fungi, an essential component of their diet.

Other factors studied in association with flying squirrel populations are the availability of cavities for nest sites (Carey 1991, Carey *et al.* 1992, Waters and Zabel 1995), understory cover (Waters and Zabel 1995) and predation (Carey *et al.* 1992).

The home range of flying squirrels was studied using radio telemetry in W. Oregon. The mean home range for *Glaucomys sabrinus* was found to be 3.4 to 4.9 ha (Bendel and Gates 1987). They found that the home range of adult males was 0.41-3.9 ha and was greater than the home range of juveniles. Adult female core territories were not found to overlap with each other. Gilmore and Gates (1985) estimated the home range of adult *Glaucomys volans* to be 3.49 ha for females and 1.89 ha for males.

Nest characteristics and nesting behavior of Northern Flying Squirrels (Mowrey and Zasada 1984) and Southern Flying Squirrels (Gilmore and Gates 1985, Bendel and Gates 1987) and communal nesting of Southern Flying Squirrels (Layne and Raymond 1994) have been observed.

Weigl and Osgood (1974) observed a biphasic nocturnal activity pattern in the Northern Flying Squirrel. The systematics, biogeography (Braun 1988) and the growth and development of the Southern Flying Squirrels have been investigated (Linzey and Linzey 1971). The body proportions of flying squirrels and the aerodynamics of gliding have also been extensively researched (Thorington and Heaney 1981, Thorington *et al.* 1988).

While studies on temperate flying squirrels have been extensive and have intensively covered many aspects of their ecology and behaviour, tropical squirrels are less intensively studied. In the tropics, while flying squirrels in Southeast Asia are being studied, there is virtually no information on the ecology, habitat requirements or behaviour of flying squirrels in India despite the diversity of flying squirrels found in this country. More research has to be encouraged in order to understand the biology of the various species of flying squirrels.

3. STUDY SITE

The study was carried out in a rainforest fragment in the Anamalai Hills, Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, southern Western Ghats. The Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary ($10^{\circ} 13'2''$ -- $10^{\circ} 33'3''$ N to $76^{\circ} 49'3''$ -- $77^{\circ} 21'4''$ E) covers 958 km and is one of the largest protected areas in South India. The sanctuary encompasses rainforest fragments ranging from one hectare to 2500 ha in size, these being remnants of what was once the most extensive and contiguous rainforest in the Western Ghats (Prabhakar 1998). Many of the smaller fragments are privately owned, while the larger fragments are owned by the forest department. Most of these fragments were created between 1860 and 1978 when the forests were leased to planters, most of them Britishers, for the cultivation of tea, coffee, cardamom, eucalyptus, rubber and teak. The construction of reservoirs, railway lines and roads led to further loss of forests.

The study site, Puduthottam (Figure 1), is located in the central part of the sanctuary, where there are about 130 km² of privately owned tea, coffee, cardamom and cinchona estates. Most of the rainforest fragments in this area, including Puduthottam, are privately owned.

3.1 LOCATION AND HISTORY

Puduthottam, situated at $10^{\circ} 20'N$ and $76^{\circ} 58' E$ at an altitude of 1085 m, was formed in 1906, when the surrounding areas were clearfelled for tea plantations, leaving about 65 ha of forest (Congreve 1938). The fragment, presently 50 ha in size and surrounded by tea and coffee plantations, is isolated, with no corridor linking it to other fragments. The nearest large fragment, Akkamalai, is 4 km away. The Valparai Pollachi state highway borders the fragment for about 2 km. The forest was underplanted with coffee and cardamom and has a history of selective logging, the last time being in 1992 (Prabhakar 1998). Being a small fragment, it is highly disturbed with tree felling and fuel wood collection being regular practices.

3.2 CLIMATE AND VEGETATION

The site receives an annual rainfall of approx. 3000 mm from both the southwest monsoon (June-Sept.) and the northeast monsoon (Oct-Nov). The vegetation has been classified as Western Tropical wet evergreen forest (West Coast tropical evergreen forest) (Champion and Seth 1968). The climax vegetation type found is a *Mesua-Cullenia-Palaquium* association.

3.3 OTHER FAUNA AT THE SITE

Puduthottam also supports other arboreal and terrestrial mammals. The mammals found in the fragment are the Lion-tailed Macaque, Malabar Giant Squirrel, Brown Palm Civet, Small Indian Civet, mongooses, sambar, muntjac, mouse deer, gaur, and a variety of other rodents. There are also reports of leopard, tiger, and other small carnivore sightings by the locals. The fragment serves as a migratory refuge for elephants.

INDIRA GANDHI WILDLIFE SANCTUARY

Figure 1: Map of the study site in Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary

4. METHODS

The study was carried out between December 1999 and March 2000.

4.1 ESTIMATION OF VEGETATION PARAMETERS

Thirty-four point quarters (Cottam and Curtis 1956) were laid along various trails through the forest and along the forest edge. Plots were laid 10 m to the left and right of the trail, alternating at 100m intervals. In each plot, the distance to the nearest tree (≥ 30 cm GBH) in each of the four quadrats, the GBH and the species of tree were recorded. Canopy cover readings were taken with a clinometer.

All the trees in the plots were searched for cavities, and any cavities seen were characterised. This was used to estimate the availability of potential nest cavities for the flying squirrel.

4.2 FEEDING HABITS OF *PETAURISTA PHILIPPENSIS*

All records of feeding were made by direct observation of the animals in the wild. Trails were walked inside the forest and along the edge between 1830 and 2230, though all hours of the night were sampled. Flashlights and a spotlight were used, along with a pair of 7 X 50 binoculars. The vegetation was thoroughly scanned at all levels and angles by the observer and one, occasionally, two field assistants. Most animals were initially detected by eyeshine and then identified with the help of binoculars.

Once a squirrel was identified, the tree species it was on, the height of the tree, the height of the animal on the tree and behaviour of the animal were recorded. When a squirrel was seen feeding, the part that was consumed and the phenophase of the part was noted. This method of diet calculation emphasises the diversity of various items ingested by the squirrel but gives no data on the amount of each species consumed (Paschoal and Galetti 1995).

Characteristics of the trees the squirrels were seen feeding on and the vegetation parameters around the feeding tree were recorded. The parameters measured were the girth of the feeding tree, canopy cover and canopy contiguity of the feeding tree and

presence/absence of cavities. The presence/absence of understory in increasing height class intervals was recorded at the feeding tree. The distance to the four trees nearest to the feeding tree and the GBH of these trees were recorded. The same vegetational parameters were quantified for random trees to measure parameters in the general habitat.

The density and dominance of tree species at the site were calculated using the software package KREBSWIN Version 3.1.

4.3 CHARACTERIZATION OF NESTING SITES

Tree cavities were identified as flying squirrel nests when the animals were observed exiting their cavities after sunset or entering their cavities just before daybreak. The field sampling protocol followed was as described above.

All the animals seen exiting their nest sites during the course of this study remained partially inside the cavities with the head and neck alone outside for a few minutes before exiting. It was at this time that a hollow was identified as a nest hollow. No indirect signs were relied upon for the location of nest cavities.

Once a nest cavity was identified, the following characteristics of the cavity were recorded - the height of the cavity on the tree, the diameter of the tree at nest height, the shape of the cavity entrance (circular, horizontal oval, longitudinal oval), length and width of the cavity entrance, the orientation of the cavity entrance, possible mode of cavity formation (natural causes - wood rot/ excavation by primary hole nesters) and location of the cavity on the tree (trunk/ branch). The nest trees were also searched for other cavities, and when present, the characteristics of these cavities were also recorded.

Characteristics of the nest tree and various vegetational parameters around the nest tree were quantified. The characteristics of the nest tree that were measured were GBH, the height of the tree, the height of the cavity on the tree, canopy cover (measured with a spherical crown densiometer), canopy contiguity of the nest tree and presence/ absence of understory in increasing height class intervals at the nest tree. The vegetation parameters recorded were the distance to the four trees nearest to the nest tree and the GBH of these trees. These trees were also searched for the presence of cavities, and any cavities seen were characterised. The same vegetational parameters were quantified for random trees

located 50 m away from the nest tree in a random direction (determined by a random twist of a compass) to measure parameters in the general habitat.

The statistical software package SPSS (Norusis 1990) was used for analysis and to test for the significance of the variables.

4.4 DENSITY ESTIMATES

The density of the flying squirrels was estimated from sighting data along the feeding trails on the road (edge habitat) was used to estimate density. The length of the trail was 1.5 km. Trees the flying squirrels were seen on were marked, and the actual perpendicular distance from the base of the tree to the trail was measured subsequently. Wherever the trail was curved, the shortest perpendicular distance was measured.

The programme DISTANCE 3.5 Version (Laake et al. 1993) was used to estimate density. Guidelines following Buckland *et al.* (1993) were used to analyse transect data.

5. RESULTS

5.1 FOREST STRUCTURE AND COMPOSITION

Two habitat types were identified at the study site - the forest interior and the forest edge, the edge being an ecotone of forest and plantations.

Stand density, Basal area and Canopy Cover

The density of trees ha⁻¹ seemed to vary in the two habitat types. Stand density in the forest interior (270 trees ha⁻¹) appeared greater than the stand density at the edge (50 trees ha⁻¹) (Table 1). Mean GBH did not differ significantly between the two habitats (Kolmogorov-Smirnov two-sample test, $z = 1.23$, $p = 0.097$). There was a significant difference in the percentage of canopy cover in the two habitat types (Kolmogorov-Smirnov two-sample test, $z = 1.417$, $p = 0.036$). The percent canopy cover was more in the forest interior than at the edge (Table 1).

Table 1: Comparison of habitat parameters between the forest interior and edge.

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Forest interior*</i> (<i>n = 80</i>)	<i>Edge*</i> (<i>n = 56</i>)
Stand density (trees ha ⁻¹)	270 ± 0.000342	50 ± 9.09e-005
Mean GBH (cm)	1.12 ± 0.13	1.49 ± 0.14
Percent Canopy cover	94.29 ± 0.67	89.74 ± 2.21

* Mean ± S.E. ; n = no. of sampling units

Girth class distribution

In the forest interior, 68.75% of all trees were of less than 100 cm GBH, while at the edge, 55.36% of the population lay between 100 and 200 cm GBH (Table 2). While shade trees planted simultaneously over coffee plantations might explain the clumped girth class distribution of trees at the edge, the concentration of individuals in the lower girth classes in the forest interior is probably indicative of a regenerating population.

When both habitats are combined, the girth class 30 - 60 cm contains the highest percentage of individuals, and the girth class 350-450 cm contains the lowest (Fig. 2). The girth class 450-550 cm comprised 2.21% of the population. All trees in this girth class were restricted to the forest interior.

Table 2: Comparison of girth class distribution of trees in the forest interior and edge.

Class Interval	Interior (%)	Edge (%)
30-60	8.93	42.50
60-100	17.86	26.25
100-150	30.36	3.75
150-200	25.00	11.25
200-250	3.57	6.25
250-350	12.50	5.00
350-450	7.79	1.25
450-550	0	3.75

Figure 2: Population structure of trees in Puduthottam (forest interior and edge pooled)

Species composition

A total of 34 tree species were recorded for the entire site, with more species found in the interior (22 species) than at the edge (16 species). Only three species (*Maesopsis*

Table 3: Species composition and relative abundance (%) of species in the forest interior and at the edge.

Species	Interior (n=20)	Edge (n=14)
<i>Maesopsis emini</i>	23.75	10.71
<i>Dimocarpus longan</i>	3.75	-
<i>Diospyrous sp.</i>	1.25	-
<i>Cassaria rubescens</i>	3.75	-
<i>Mesua ferrea</i>	8.75	-
<i>Macaranga sp.</i>	17.5	-
<i>Phyllanthus sp.</i>	1.25	-
<i>Holigarna nigra</i>	1.25	-
<i>Spathodea companulata</i>	2.5	-
<i>Mesa indica</i>	11.25	-
<i>Syzygium hemisphericum</i>	1.25	-
<i>Cullenia exarillata</i>	2.50	1.79
<i>Myristica dactiloides</i>	3.75	-
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	2.5	21.43
<i>Clerodendron sp.</i>	6.25	-
<i>Mallotus tetracoccus</i>	1.25	-
<i>Dysoxylum malabaricum</i>	1.25	-
<i>Antidesma menesu</i>	1.25	-
<i>Bhesa indica</i>	1.25	-
<i>Cinnamomum sulphuratum</i>	1.25	-
<i>Cryptocarya sp.</i>	1.25	-
<i>Nothopegia racemosa</i>	1.25	-
<i>Toona ciliata</i>	-	5.36
<i>Persea macarantha</i>	-	1.79
<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	-	3.75
<i>Syzygium zeylanicum</i>	-	1.79
<i>Grevelia robusta</i>	-	16.07
<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	-	3.57
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	-	1.79
<i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>	-	14.29
<i>Elaeocarpus serratus</i>	-	1.79
<i>Trichelia connoroides</i>	-	1.79
<i>Erythrina sp.</i>	-	7.14
<i>Dalbergia sp.</i>	-	3.57
<i>Prunus ceylanica</i>	-	1.79

n = no of sampling units

emini, *Artocarpus heterophyllus* and *Cullenia exarillata*) were common to both habitat types.

The most abundant species at the edge were *Artocarpus heterophyllus* (21.43%), *Grevelia robusta* (16.07%), *Eucalyptus sp.* (14.29%) and *Maesopsis emini* (10.71%)

(Table 3). *G. robusta* and *Eucalyptus* are planted for timber and as shade trees in tea plantations and along roadsides. *M. emini* is planted as a shade tree in coffee plantations. *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, a native species, is abundant in coffee plantations and near human settlements. *Artocarpus heterophyllus* might have been planted as a shade tree or for other purposes and this might explain the higher densities at the forest edge. The most abundant species in the forest interior were *Maesopsis emini* (23.75%), *Macaranga* sp. (17.50%), *Mesa indica* (11.25%), and *Mesua ferrea* (8.75%) (Table 3). *Maesopsis emini* and *Macaranga* are pioneer or secondary species, quick to invade both natural gaps and areas cleared by humans. *Maesopsis*, a plantation species, is known to self-seed and rapidly develop large soil seed banks, as has been seen in the East Usambara Mountains, Africa, where its removal is a long-term conservation goal (Hamilton and Benstead-Smith 1990). The fruits of *Maesopsis emini* are also consumed by a wide variety of mammals (Lion-tailed Macaque, Malabar Giant Squirrel, etc) and birds at the site. The high density of *M. emini* in the forest interior may be explained by both its regenerative qualities and the dispersal of the species by frugivores. Members of the genus *Macaranga* are highly successful early successional species found throughout the far east (Whitmore 1984). The high abundance of these species is indicative of the level of disturbance at the site.

When both sub-habitats were pooled, *Mesua ferrea* had the highest basal area (6.53), though the relative density of the species was low (5.15%). *Artocarpus heterophyllus* had a basal area of 4.33 and a relative density of 10.29%. Other abundant species, *Maesopsis emini* (18.38%), *Macaranga* sp.(10.29%) had lower basal areas (1.89 and 0.32 respectively) indicating that most of the individuals were in the smaller girth classes (Appendix-Table A1).

Cavities were seen in 20 out of the 136 trees examined. Multiple cavities were seen in seven trees. Since it could not be ascertained if multiple cavities on a tree were multiple entrances to one cavity or if they were entrances to different cavities, trees were scored as having cavities or not having cavities. Cavity availability is estimated to be 19.05 cavities ha⁻¹.

5.2 FLYING SQUIRREL ECOLOGY

5.2a FOOD HABITS

Petaurista philippensis was sighted 322 times during the course of the study. This is the number of positive identifications – the number of observations when eyeshine was seen but the animal moved away from sight before positive identification is excluded from analysis. It was observed feeding on 103 occasions.

During the study period, which was mainly in the dry season, flying squirrels consumed a total of 10 species of plants from 8 different families and at least 25 different plant parts (Table 4). There was one observation of the flying squirrel feeding on lichens from the bark of *Macaranga* sp.

During the study period, flying squirrels were seen to consume fruit more than any other plant part (Fig 3). Of this semi-ripe fruit was seen being consumed in 9.80% of the observations, while ripe fruit was seen being consumed in 6.86% of the observations (Table 4). Leaves were seen being consumed in 39.21% of the observations, and mature leaves were seen being consumed in 8.82% of the observations, while immature leaves were seen being consumed in 7.84% of the observations. However, the phenophase of leaves could not be ascertained in a large proportion of the observations.

All the fruits consumed were of the species *Ficus racemosa*. Leaves of *Ficus racemosa* were consumed more than the leaves of any other species (17.65%). Only flowers of *Cullenia exarillata* were being consumed. Flying squirrels were seen eating the bark of *Eucalyptus* (7.84%), *Mesua ferrea* (0.98%) and *Dimocarpus longan* (0.98%).

The average height at which the squirrels were observed feeding was 16.67 m and the average height of feeding trees was 28.75 m (n= 43).

Feeding site selection

Analysis of the characteristics of feeding tree plots to random tree plots revealed that the total canopy contiguity significantly differed between the two plots (Kolmogorov-Smirnov two-sample test, $z = 1.398$, $p = 0.40$). Feeding tree plots had greater total canopy contiguity (6.782 ± 0.724) than random tree plots (2.82 ± 0.6779).

Table 4: Plant species in the diet of *Petaurista philippensis* and the percentage of parts consumed

<i>Species</i>	<i>Part cons.</i>	<i>Pheno-phase*</i>	<i>No. of obs/ phenophase</i>	<i>No. of obs/part</i>	<i>Total obs/sp</i>	<i>% obs/s p</i>
<i>Cullenia exarillata</i>	flower	-	9	9	9	8.82
<i>Mesua ferrea</i>	bark	-	1	1	1	0.98
<i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>	bark	-	5	5	5	4.90
<i>Dimocarpus longan</i>	bark	-	1	1	5	4.90
	leaf	imm.	2	4		
	leaf	uid	2			
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	leaf	m	1	6	6	5.88
	leaf	uid	5			
<i>Ficus callosa</i>	leaf	m	1	1	1	0.98
<i>Ficus amplissima</i>	leaf	m	1	2	2	1.96
	leaf	uid	1			
<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	leaf	imm	4	18	64	62.75
	leaf	m.	3			
	leaf	uid	11			
	fruit	ur	4	46		
	fruit	sr	10			
	fruit	r	7			
	fruit	ur & sr	3			
	fruit	ur & r	4			
	fruit	uid	18			
<i>Persea macarantha</i>	leaf	uid	1	1	1	0.98
Total					102	100

* codes for phenological phase of plant parts consumed - leaf: imm.-immature; m-mature; uid-unidentified. fruit: ur-unripe; sr-semi-ripe; r-ripe; ur & sr-unripe and semi ripe fruits consumed ; ur & r-unripe and ripe; uid-unidentified.

Figure 3: Percentage observation of parts consumed

Though there was no marked preference for trees of any particular girth class, flying squirrels used trees of girth 250-350 cm more than other girth classes (Fig 4). GBH is assumed to be an indicator of tree size and reflects the tree's ability to produce fruit (Chapman 1988).

Figure 4: Distribution of GBH of feeding trees and available trees

5.2b NESTING BEHAVIOUR

Flying squirrels were observed exiting nests on 9 occasions and entering a cavity on one occasion. On one occasion, two squirrels were seen exiting from the same hollow within three minutes of each other. On another occasion, two squirrels were seen exiting from two different cavities on the same tree within 12 minutes of each other. All observations of nest exit by flying squirrels were within 88.22 ± 9.52 (n=9) minutes after sunset.

Nest cavity characteristics

Five nest cavities were on *Mesua ferrea*, one on *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, one on *Dimocarpus longan* and one on *Toona ciliata*. Three of the nest trees were half dead. 50% of the nest cavities were oriented towards the South West (Fig. 5). Nest cavities were located at an average height of 18.6m, and the average height of the trees was 41.88 m. The average GBH of nest trees was 3.35 m, and the diameter at nest height was 1.72 m (Table 5). Four of the cavities were round in shape, while six were oval. Two of the oval cavities were longitudinally oval, while the rest were horizontally oval. Seven of the ten cavities were located on the trunk of the tree, and three were on the primary branch.

Figure 5: Orientation of nest cavities

Only two cavities appeared to be excavated by primary hole nesters, the rest seemed to be natural cavities caused by heart rot where limbs had broken away. The average cavity length and width were 18.58 cm and 14.93 cm (Table 5).

Table 5: Nest cavity characteristics

<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>S.E.</i>	<i>n</i>
Tree height (m)	41.88	2.172	10
Height of cavity on tree (m)	18.6	1.847	10
GBH of tree (m)	3.35	0.226	10
DNH* (m)	1.72	0.239	9**
Cavity length (cm)	15.61	3.473	9**
Cavity width (cm)	13.05	2.249	9**

*DNH - Diameter at Nest Height.

**Length, Width and DNH of one upward facing cavity could not be ascertained.

Nest site selection

Analysis of characteristics at nest sites and random sites revealed that the girth of the nest trees was significantly greater than that of the random trees (Kolmogorov-Smirnov two-sample test, $z = 2.0$, $p = 0.01$). Flying squirrels showed a marked preference for trees of larger GBH (Fig 6).

Figure 6: Distribution of GBH of nest trees and random trees

5.2c SOCIAL BEHAVIOUR

Intra-specific interactions

Flying squirrels were seen in groups on 46 occasions. By groups, it meant that two or more two flying squirrels were seen together on the same tree. They were seen in pairs on 32 occasions and were seen in groups of three on 12 occasions. Groups larger than three were rare, and this was seen on two occasions.

Most groups were seen on feeding trees, and when groups of more than two individuals were seen, at least one squirrel was engaged in feeding. When flying squirrels were seen in pairs, both squirrels were seen feeding in more than 40% of the observations. On two occasions, pairs were seen exiting nest cavities on the same tree. On two occasions, squirrels were seen grooming each other. The age class (young, juvenile, adult) and sex of squirrels could not be determined with accuracy on all occasions.

Potential Competitors

Few other arboreal and nocturnal mammals are found at Puduthottam that might pose competition for the large brown flying squirrel. The Lion-tailed Macaque (*Macaca silenus*), a diurnal primate, is found at the site. Three species of diurnal squirrels are found at the site, the Malabar Giant Squirrel (*Ratufa indica*), the Western Ghats Dusky Striped Squirrel (*Funambulus sulinatus*) and the Jungle Striped Squirrel (*Funambulus tristriatus*).

The scansorial nocturnal Brown Palm Civet (*Paradoxorus jerdonii*) is found at the study site. On various occasions, Brown Palm Civets have been seen feeding on *Cullenia exarillata*, *Ficus racemosa* and *Elaocarpus* sp. On one occasion, a Brown Palm Civet and three flying squirrels were seen together on a *Ficus racemosa* tree. All four individuals were feeding on the fruits, and no interspecific aggression seen. Brown Palm Civets are known to use cavities for nesting, and on one occasion, a Brown Palm Civet was seen exiting a cavity. Another species of nocturnal civet, the Small Indian Civet, was also seen at Puduthottam.

Predators

During the study period, there were no records of any predation on the large brown flying squirrels.

5.2d DENSITY

22 transects were walked, and this was used to compute the density of flying squirrels at the site. All the transects were walked along the edge of the fragment, as Large Brown Flying Squirrels were encountered more frequently along the fragment edge than in other habitats. Various habitat types (forest interior, edge and plantations) were walked, and the encounter rate of flying squirrels in each of these habitats was calculated. No flying squirrels were sighted in tea plantations, and all the sightings in plantations were restricted to coffee plantations.

Table 6: Encounter rates of flying squirrels in various habitat types at Puduthottam

<i>Habitat</i>	<i>Total length walked (l)</i>	<i>No. of sightings (n)</i>	<i>Encounter rate* (n/l)</i>
Forest interior	9.6	38	3.95
Edge	40.25	246	6.11
Plantations	3.375	19	5.62

*- Encounter rate is expressed as no of sightings/ km of walk.

The encounter rate was highest at the forest edge (6.1 individuals/ km), lowest in the forest interior (3.92 individuals/ km) (Table 6). The encounter rate in the plantations (5.62 individuals/ km) may not reflect the true usage of the habitat. This is as most sightings in the plantations were close to the edge and the squirrels might have been moving from the edge. No squirrels were sighted in the interior regions of the plantations.

The density estimate of the large brown flying squirrel at the edge habitat at Puduthottam was calculated as 2.59 individuals ha⁻¹.

Table 7: Density of large brown flying squirrels in the edge habitat, Puduthottam

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>%CV</i>	<i>95%CI</i>
D _s	1.955	14.57	1.46-2.61
D	2.59	15.36	1.91-3.51

D_s : Denstiy of animal clusters per km²; D : Density of animals per km²

Table 8: Details of model used to estimate density

<i>Model used</i>	<i>No. of adjustment terms used</i>	<i>f(0)</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>ESW</i>	<i>AIC value</i>
Uniform cosine	3	0.714	0.34	14.06	940.88

f(0)-avgerage probability density function; p-average detection probability in area surveyed; ESW- Effective strip width ; AIC- Akaike's Information Criteria value

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 FEEDING BEHAVIOR

During the study period, the diet of *Petaurista philippensis* seemed to consist predominantly of fruits and leaves. There were no observations of *P. philippensis* feeding on insects or animal matter.

The fruits of *Ficus racemosa* were consumed more than any other food item. However, the high consumption of the fruits of *Ficus racemosa* despite the low abundance and dominance of the species at the study site does not necessarily imply a preference for the species. The study was carried out in the dry season, and very few species apart from *F. racemosa* seemed to be in fruit. *Mesua ferrea* was fruiting, and though Malabar Giant squirrels (*Ratufa indica*) were seen eating the fruit, flying squirrels were never seen to do so. *Cullenia exarillata* was flowering and fruiting, but flying squirrels were only observed to eat the flowers. Flying squirrels have also been observed consuming the flowers of *C. exarillata* at Kakachi (Ganesh and Davidar 1997), but there are no records of flying squirrels consuming the fruits of this species. *Artocarpus heterophyllus* was beginning to fruit towards the end of the study period. Though there are records of *Petaurista petaurista* consuming the fruit/seed of this species in Malaysia (Barrett, Ph. D. Dissertation), this was not observed during this study. The consumption of the fruits of *F. racemosa* by *Petaurista philippensis* may be correlated with food availability rather than reflect a preference for the food item.

Groups of up to four individuals were seen on *F. racemosa* when the species was fruiting. More groups of flying squirrels were seen on this species than on any other food tree species, possibly implying that the flying squirrels were congregating at a resource. The role of figs as important resources for frugivore communities during periods of food scarcity has been established in rain forests in Peru (Terborgh 1983) and in East Kalimantan (Leighton and Leighton 1983). In a study on the Malabar Giant Squirrel, Borges (1993) has shown that figs are a lean fruiting season resource only for those individuals who have access to figs within their territories or feeding ranges and suggests that figs can be utilised as a major fruit source only by a mobile species with a large home range. Large Brown Flying Squirrels can cover large distances by gliding (a flying

squirrel was seen to cover a distance of 92.4 m in one glide at Puduthottam), and are known to have large home ranges. This would greatly increase their ability to track food resources. The large number of groups of *P. philippensis* seen on *Ficus racemosa* more than on any other food resource might suggest the exploitation of figs as a major fruit source.

In the current study, for the cases when the phenological phase of the leaves being consumed could be identified, it was seen that flying squirrels consumed more mature leaves than young leaves. Young leaves are known to be more nutritious and less tough and fibrous than older leaves (Coley 1982). Kawamichi (1997), in a long-term study of food habits of Japanese Flying Squirrels *Petaurista leucogynys*, used the proportion of mature leaves eaten each month as a negative index of food availability. In the current study, flying squirrels were also seen to consume more leaves in the months of December and February, when *Ficus racemosa* did not seem to fruit as abundantly as in January. However, it cannot be assumed from this that flying squirrels consumed more leaves or mature leaves during periods of lower food availability as long term phenological and nutritional studies are required to supplement diet studies before such conclusions can be arrived at.

It has been hypothesized that flying squirrels meet the protein requirements of their diet from the consumption of leaves and obtain high-energy carbohydrates from fruits (Barrett, Ph. D. Dissertation). *Ficus* fruits are a source of easily assimilated energy, with low fat content and are a potential source of animal proteins (which is provided by the larvae of fig wasps inside the figs) (Vellayan 1981). Flying squirrels were seen eating the bark of three tree species. While bark and the woody parts of plants are generally high in cellulose, the flying squirrels may have eaten the bark of *Eucalyptus* sp. to obtain the resins and exudates. In areas disturbed by logging squirrels have been seen to respond to reduced food availability by increasing consumption of bark and sap (Johns 1985).

6.2 NESTING BEHAVIOUR

Flying squirrels showed a preference towards nesting in the cavities of large trees. This may either be due to the presence of cavities only in such large mature trees or may be a selective choice towards large trees. The proportional utilisation of the larger girth classes was high, while the trees in the lower girth classes were underutilised. Proportional utilisation of trees in larger girth classes was also higher than the proportion of available trees in these girth classes (Fig 6). These girth classes are composed of native remnant rainforest species such as *Mesua ferrea*, *Cullenia exarillata* and *Alstonia scholaris*, and these may be trees that have been left behind during selective logging operations. In Malaysia, such trees provided refuge to Red Giant Flying Squirrels (*Petaurista petaurista*) and prevented populations from declining after logging operations (Johns 1983). In a disturbed habitat such as Puduthottam, these large trees that have been left standing during logging operations could serve as refuges for flying squirrels and other hole-nesting species.

Three of the nests were located in trees that were not completely alive and that had partially dead branches. The importance of snags or dead trees in forest systems has been well documented. Gibbons and Lindenmayer (1997) stress the importance of dead trees for hollow-dwelling fauna in Australian eucalypt forests and recommend that these trees be retained during logging operations. Such trees provide refuge for a wide variety of mammals and birds and form an important component of the habitat.

All the nests located during the study period were located either within the forest interior or amidst a remnant patch of rainforest when the nests were located at the edge. No nests were seen in the plantations, and none were seen on shade trees or on introduced tree species, though the density of these species was high. Flying squirrels seemed to prefer large trees in mature forest stands as nest sites. This could be because older trees might have more and better-developed cavities or because taller, larger trees might provide greater protection from predators.

Most nests were located in *Mesua ferrea*. One nest was seen in *Artocarpus heteropyllus* and one in *Toona ciliata*. All of the trees contain sap or resin, and it can be inferred from this that the large brown flying squirrel was not deterred by the presence of

sap or resin, unlike Southern Flying Squirrels (*Glaucomys volans*), which were seen to avoid tree resin (Schaefer and Saenz 1998).

On a few occasions, flying squirrels were seen nesting in pairs in either the same or different cavities on a single tree. It is not known if the different cavities were connected and if the hollows were multiple entrances to one cavity, or if flying squirrels occupied different cavities on the same tree. Most of the nest trees (75%) had more than one cavity on the tree. During the course of this study, a maximum of two squirrels were seen occupying a nest tree together. Communal nesting of Southern Flying Squirrels (*Glaucomys volans*) is common in temperate regions, where aggregations of up to 50 squirrels have been seen in one cavity (Gilmore and Gates 1985). Temperate flying squirrels are thought to nest together in large aggregations in order to reduce energy expenditure for maintaining body temperatures in cold weather. An alternate explanation is that it plays a significant role in social organisation and that it confers social benefits like stress reduction, increased success in finding mates and predator avoidance (Layne and Raymond 1994). Such large aggregations have not been recorded in the tropics. As temperatures are not as adverse in the tropics as in the temperate regions, communal nesting cannot be said to be prompted by a need for thermoregulation. Social relationships might explain the pair nesting of flying squirrels seen at Puduthottam. On one occasion, one individual of the pair that emerged from the hollow seemed smaller and less agile than the other. It can be speculated that the pair were adult and young, but the nature of the social relationship between the two is not known. Detailed studies investigating the social nesting behaviour of this species need to be carried out before such conclusions can be arrived at.

The availability of cavities at Puduthottam was estimated to be 19.05 cavities ha⁻¹. As the cavities used by flying squirrels did not appear to be very specific in character (as seen in this study), this figure denotes availability of cavities in general and is not specific to a particular size, class or shape. This figure appears to be higher than the availability of potential cavities for the Malabar Grey Hornbill, which was estimated at 10 cavities ha⁻¹ (Mudappa and Kannan 1997). In the absence of cavities flying squirrels in the temperate regions were observed using other structures for nesting (stick nests and witches broom) (Mowrey and Zasada 1984). In the Chin Valley, Burma, *Petaurista candidulus* and *Petaurista sybilla* were observed to nest in stick nests as well as in tree hollows. They

were observed to build their own nests as well as use the old stick nests or drays of *Ratufa* sp. (Mackenzie 1916). It is not known if this nesting behaviour was in response to reduced cavity availability. This nesting behaviour has not been recorded for *P. philippensis* and was not observed at this study site.

6.3 COMPETITION

The occurrence of several species of birds and mammals utilising similar resources might pose competition to the large brown flying squirrel at Puduthottam.

During the study period, the only other mammal seen to utilize nest cavities was the Brown Palm Civet (*Paradoxorous jerdoni*). However, the Brown Palm Civet is also known to use other resources for nesting (a tangle of lianas, etc.), and this may reduce competition for cavities. Several hole-nesting species of birds (Malabar Grey Hornbills, Great Pied hornbills, Hill Mynas, and Woodpeckers) are found at Puduthottam. Though only one instance of active competition was observed, their occurrence might increase the pressure on available cavities. During the study period, a pair of Malabar Grey Hornbills were seen to displace a flying squirrel from a hollow. In this case, two weeks after the flying squirrel was seen using the hollow, a pair was Malabar Grey Hornbills (*Ocyrceros griseus*) were seen nesting in the same hollow. The size and features of the hollows utilised by flying squirrels during the study period varied and did not reflect a strong preference for any particular characteristics of the hollow like entrance size or orientation. Flying squirrels are probably not exclusive or permanent users of a cavity and might occupy temporarily vacant cavities. In North America, Southern Flying Squirrels (*Glaucomys volans*) have been observed to move to new cavities often, and females have been observed to move their young frequently, presumably to avoid infestation by fleas (Bendel and Gates 1987). No such information is available on the nesting habits of the *Petaurista philippensis*, and the nesting behaviour of the species must be studied in greater detail to ascertain the actual cavity requirements.

Several species of arboreal mammals were seen to consume similar food resources. The Lion-tailed Macaque (*Macaca silenus*), a diurnal primate is found at the site and has been seen to consume similar food species - *Cullenia exarillata*, *Ficus spp.*, *Macaranga peltata*, *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, *Mesua ferrea*, *Elaeocarpus spp.*, etc. (Menon).

Though there was a similarity in the food species utilised by the Lion-tailed Macaques and flying squirrels, there was a difference in the plant parts consumed. Lion-tailed Macaques were seen to consume only a very small proportion of leaves, and their diet consisted mainly of flowers, fruit flesh and seeds (Menon), whereas the flying squirrels were seen to consume more fruit and leaves. Tree squirrels are primarily adapted for feeding on tree seeds (Kieth 1965). The Malabar Giant Squirrels (*Ratufa indica*) diet has been seen to consist predominantly of seeds, though it is known to be a facultative frugivore and consumes leaves, flowers, pith and bark during non-fruiting periods (Ramachandran 1988; Borges 1992, 1993). Consumption of different plant parts separates the different species into different niches and might result in the partitioning of resources, thus reducing interspecific competition for food resources. This might explain the co-occurrence of the various species at the same site. Their diurnal habits also reduce contact with the flying squirrel, and this additionally reduces the pressure on resources.

The most direct contender for food resources might be the Brown Palm Civet, as it is also nocturnal and largely frugivorous. However, in this case, as well, the species may occupy different niches based on their dietary preferences or their arboreal nature. The Brown Palm Civet is not completely arboreal but scansorial. It also forages on the ground, unlike the Large Brown Flying Squirrels, which are arboreal. Their arboreal and scansorial natures might confine them to different forest strata, partitioning resources and reducing interspecific competition.

The other species of flying squirrel found in the Western Ghats, the Small Travancore Flying Squirrel (*Petinomys fuscocapillus*) has been reported to occur in some of the rainforest fragments of the Anamalai hills (Umapathy and Kumar in press). As the species is rare and it has been difficult to distinguish between the Large Brown Flying Squirrel and the Small Travancore Flying Squirrel species, museum specimens of the skins of both species were examined. The rarer Small Travancore Flying Squirrel was not sighted during the study period, and all the flying squirrels seen were identified as Large Brown Flying Squirrels.

6.4 DENSITY

The encounter rates in different habitats in Puduthottam varied, with the encounter rates being the highest at the forest edge, followed by the encounter rate in the plantations (Table 7). The encounter rate in the plantations may not reflect the proper use of the habitat. Most sightings in the plantations were near the edge, and it might have been that animals strayed into the plantations from the edge habitat. There might have been an overlap of habitat use by the same individuals, and this might have increased the encounter rate seen in the plantations.

The encounter rate for flying squirrels at the edge was higher than the encounter rate in the forest interior. This could be due to the fact that the visibility is greater along the edge. The density of trees at the forest edge was found to be almost five times lower than the density of trees in the forest interior, and this might increase visibility. However, other factors might also contribute to the higher encounter rate at the forest edge. During the study period, the flying squirrels were seen to consume the fruits of *Ficus racemosa* more than any other food item. Figs are known to be present at low densities in forest ecosystems and individual trees are usually clumped (Gautier-Hion and Michaloud 1989). These trends were seen at Puduthottam, where the species was only recorded at the edge (Table 3). The forest interior had very few fig trees, and they were spatially distributed. At the edge, individuals of *Ficus racemosa* were seen to occur in clumps. As has already been explained, the flying squirrels were seen to congregate at the food trees possibly as very few other species were in fruit. This might have artificially inflated the encounter rate of flying squirrels at the edge.

In a study on the relative densities of the two species of flying squirrels in the Western Ghats, Ashraf *et al.* (1993) found that *Petaurista philippensis* was encountered most in cardamom plantations (1.5 sightings/ hr) followed by deciduous forests (1.2 sightings/hr) (Encounter rate/ km was obtained from the details provided by the authors in order to make the data comparable to the encounter rates generated in the current study).

From their study it could be seen that the encounter rate of flying squirrels was highest in a disturbed habitat (cardamom plantations). In the present study, while Puduthottam itself is a disturbed habitat, it was seen that the encounter rate was highest at

the edge, where the disturbance is maximum. All the encounter rates found in this study are much higher than those reported by Ashraf *et al.* (1993), but this may be indicative of the sampling regime – only foot transects were walked in the present study, but both vehicle and foot transects were employed in the earlier one by Ashraf *et al.* (1993).

At Puduthottam, the density estimates for flying squirrels were computed for the edge habitat alone. The density estimate for *Petaurista philippensis* (2.29 ha⁻¹) at Puduthottam is higher than any previous density estimates for the species in the Western Ghats. As explained before, the increased visibility and artificial congregation of the squirrels at a food resource along the edge might be responsible for an inflated density estimate.

In many studies in the tropics, it has been seen that the populations of giant flying squirrels increase with disturbance. Umapathy and Kumar (in press) have reported that the densities of *P. philippensis* and *Petinomys fuscocapillus* together range from 0.189 individuals ha⁻¹ in a large undisturbed fragment to 0.69 individuals ha⁻¹ in a small disturbed fragment in the Annamalai hills of the Western Ghats. Population densities of *P. petaurista* at Sungai Tekam, Malaysia were higher in logged forests (0.039 squirrels ha⁻¹) than in unlogged forests (0.033 squirrels ha⁻¹) (Barret, Ph. D. Dissertation).

In Taiwan, the average density of *Petaurista petaurista* was found to be 0.235 individuals ha⁻¹ and 0.056 individuals/ha in hardwood forests and conifer plantations, respectively (Lee *et al.* 1993). It has been observed that though the populations of flying squirrels are higher in the lower elevations of hardwood forests, *P. petaurista* has recently adapted to secondary conifer plantations, where it is nearly a pest (Lee *et al.* 1986). As discussed earlier, the populations of the Red Giant Flying Squirrels were not found to decline after selective logging operations in Malaysia. Johns (1985) theorises that the loss of established nesting sites during logging operations is compensated for by new refuges created when boles or branches are snapped off by falling neighbour trees. Muul and Lim (1978) state that flying squirrels tolerate disturbance as long as the distance between trees is short enough that the squirrels can glide between trees. A decrease in predators and increased food availability may also be responsible for increased densities. However, the ecology of flying squirrels must be compared between unlogged and logged sites to explain the increase in their numbers after disturbance.

Comparison of the densities of temperate and tropical flying squirrels

Densities of flying squirrels in the temperate regions have been examined in relation to various parameters. Flying squirrel abundance has been studied in relation to forest age. Studies (Waters and Zabel 1995, Carey 1992, Rosenberg and Anthony 1992) (Table 9) suggest that higher densities of Northern Flying Squirrels are found in older forest stands. As forest clearcuts mature to a closed canopy stage, the density of flying squirrels is thought to increase. This rate of increase of flying squirrel numbers however decreases as the forest matures (Rosenberg *et al.* 1993). Waters and Zabel (1995) report that mean density of Northern Flying Squirrels *Glaucomys sabrinus* was greater in older mature stands ($2.76 \text{ ha}^{-1} + -0.55$) than in shelterwood stands ($0.31 \text{ ha}^{-1} - + 11$) and found that populations were dependent on food availability but were not affected by cavity density.

Witt (1992) reasons that the increased abundance of flying squirrels in older forests may be because of the increased availability of den sites in old growth and the presence of more favourable microclimatic conditions conducive to the growth of hypogeous fungi, which is the main food of the Northern Flying Squirrel in temperate regions.

Taulman *et al.* (1998) found that populations of Southern Flying Squirrel *Glaucomys volans* could persist in logged habitats only by when the squirrels could concentrate their activities in nearby greenbelts areas. These studies indicate that temperate flying squirrel populations are most successful in older forests.

These characteristics of the temperate flying squirrel populations seem to be different from the population trends exhibited by tropical flying squirrels – the highest densities of temperate flying squirrels are seen in mature undisturbed stands (Rosenberg *et al.* 1996), while the numbers of giant flying squirrels have been seen to increase with logging and disturbance (Johns 1983).

Explaining habitat preferences in connection with gliding locomotion, Thorington and Heaney (1981) hypothesise that the smallest species of flying squirrels are adapted to gliding in thick vegetation where there is less turbulence and slow flight speed and manoeuvrability are important. Larger species are more suited to gliding in more open areas, where the loss of manoeuvrability at higher air speeds makes them less prone to turbulent air conditions. Temperate flying squirrels are much smaller than the giant flying

squirrels found in Asia, and the above hypothesis could be applied to explain the success of different species of flying squirrels in different habitat types.

Table 9: The comparison of flying squirrel densities in various coniferous and deciduous forests in North America

<i>Species</i>	<i>Density</i> (squirrels ha ⁻¹)	<i>Location</i>	<i>Source</i>
<i>Glaucomys sabrinus</i>	2.0 2.3	young stands & old stands, Oregon cascades	Rosenberg and Anthony 1992
<i>Glaucomys sabrinus</i>	0.9 1.9 0.2 0.5	young stands, Oregon old stands, Oregon Young stands, Washington Old stands, Washington	Carey <i>et al</i> 1992
<i>Glaucomys sabrinus</i>	0.24 0.52-1.28	second growth old growth western Oregon	Witt 1992
<i>Glaucomys sabrinus</i>	3.29 0.37 2.28	old stands shelterwood stands young stands Fir forests, northeastern California	Waters and Zabel 1995
<i>Glaucomys sabrinus</i>	1.38 & 1.50 0.64 & 0.68	treatment (logged) stands control (unlogged) stands British Colombia, Canada	Ransome and Sullivan 1997
<i>Glaucomys sabrinus</i>	0.2-1.8 1.2-5.8 0.2-2.1	<i>Populus</i> dominated forests <i>Abies</i> dominated forests <i>Picea</i> dominated forests Utah	Anderson 1980
<i>Glaucomys volans</i>	0.101-- 0.493	control and treatment stands- experimental even aged and uneven aged stands, Arkansas	Taulman <i>et al</i> 1998

The preference for habitat in relation to gliding habits is a possible explanation for the higher densities of the tropical giant flying squirrels in logged areas. The densities of flying squirrels may also have increased due to increased cavity availability. However, the densities of flying squirrels may also have increased due to increased food availability. Disturbance and logging open up the canopy, and this has often been found to increase fruit production (Chivers 1972 in Dutta 1996). Predator responses to logging

also have to be considered. The success of species in disturbed habitats is determined by a complex of variables, such as the nature of the disturbance, habitat variables and socioecological characteristics of the species. Socioecological characteristics of species that might affect the success of species in modified habitats could be the percentage composition of diet, mean biomass, mean group size, group biomass, arboreal or terrestrial habits and other factors.

One of the biggest threats to wildlife today is the destruction or alteration of existing natural ecosystems. Various species react to disturbance in different ways, and knowledge of their biology, ecology and interactions with natural ecosystems is essential before management plans concerning the species can be conceived. Virtually nothing is known of the ecology of the Large Brown Flying Squirrel in India, and it is essential that the species is intensively studied in order to explain its response to disturbance. Long-term studies in natural forests are required to be carried out for a complete understanding of the ecology of the animal.

7. CONCLUSION

The vegetation at the study site was dominated by pioneer species and introduced species, with a very low percentage of the remnant original rainforest vegetation. Selective logging at the site resulted in a skewed distribution of trees. Most of the trees at the site were in the lower girth classes, indicating a growing population. Very few large trees were present at the site, and these were rainforest species, presumably left standing during logging operations. The extremely high degree of disturbance at the site was reflected in the species composition (more than half of the stand was occupied by gap-invading species) (Table 3) and in the girth class distribution of trees (Table 2). Two species, *Macaranga* and *Maesopsis emini* dominated the site. While *Macaranga* is a natural species, *M. emini* is known to be an invasive coloniser (Hamilton and Benstead-Smith 1990). The restriction of the spread of this species is imperative if the original rainforest fauna is to be restored at the site. A comparison of the edge and forest interior also revealed that the edge was more open and had lower tree density and species richness (Tables 1 & 3).

The Large Brown Flying Squirrel was seen to consume only plant matter, and there were no observations of insectivory or carnivory. Fruit and leaves were consumed more than any other plant part (Figure 2). The most important food item in the diet seemed to be the fruits of *Ficus racemosa* (Table 4), which was one of the very few species in fruit during the study period. The flying squirrel did not appear to be selective in the choice of food species, instead seemed to utilise available resources. The flying squirrel was also seen to eat the bark of three tree species and was observed consuming lichens on one occasion. Only 10 species of trees were seen in the diet, and the feeding habits of the flying squirrel need to be studied both a long term, covering all the seasons so that seasonal use of resources can be documented. The species must also be studied in a natural, undisturbed environment to know the natural requirements of the species and to understand its ability to cope in a disturbed environment.

Flying squirrels seemed to prefer to nest in large trees located in mature stands (Figure 6). No nests were observed in the plantations. Nests were not of any particular size or shape. On one occasion a pair of Malabar Grey Hornbills were seen occupying a hollow that had previously been occupied by a flying squirrel. This suggests that flying

squirrels may not be exclusive users of a cavity. All of the above could suggest that they are not choosy or particular about the cavities they occupy and that they might occupy any empty hollow. However, a more detailed examination of nesting behaviour is required to understand cavity requirements and usage.

The density of the Large Brown Flying Squirrel seemed to be high compared to other studies on giant flying squirrels in Asia. While other studies (Umapathy and Kumar, in press, Johns 1985) have documented an increase in numbers of the species with increased disturbance and logging, there are no sufficient explanations for this trend. The species needs to be studied in its natural environment to know the requirements (food sources and nesting resources) and understand how they are met in a disturbed site. The density in natural, undisturbed conditions as well as how these numbers are kept in check, is also required to be known. This implies a knowledge of the predators, competitors, and also the natural population dynamics.

To summarise, this study revealed that the Large Brown Flying Squirrel (*Petaurista philippensis*) is found in high numbers at the study site despite drastic habitat alterations due to selective logging and the pressure of human disturbance. The survival of the species may reflect that it is a generalist species rather than a specialist. However, the species required large trees in mature stands for nesting purposes. Competition from other species has not seemed to adversely affect the flying squirrel. This is perhaps it occupies a unique niche, being a nocturnal glider.

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APPENDIX

Table A1: Species-wise contribution to basal area, density, frequency and importance value index in Puduhottam (edge and interior sub-habitats pooled)

Species	BA	Relative dominance	Density	Relative density	Frequency	Relative frequency	IVI
<i>Maesopsis emini</i>	1.89	7.18	25	18.38	12	12.12	37.68
<i>Dimocarpus longan</i>	0.94	3.55	3	2.21	2	2.02	7.78
<i>Diospyrous sp.</i>	0.04	0.15	1	0.74	1	1.01	1.90
<i>Cassaria rubescens</i>	1.54	5.84	3	2.21	2	2.02	10.06
<i>Mesua ferrea</i>	6.53	24.77	7	5.15	6	6.06	35.98
<i>Macaranga sp.</i>	0.32	1.21	14	10.29	9	9.09	20.60
<i>Phyllanthus sp.</i>	0.01	0.04	1	0.74	1	1.01	1.78
<i>Holigarna nigra</i>	0.19	0.72	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.47
<i>Spathodea companulata</i>	0.09	0.34	2	1.47	2	2.02	3.84
<i>Mesa indica</i>	0.10	0.39	9	6.62	7	7.07	14.08
<i>Syzygium hemisphericum</i>	0.01	0.04	1	0.74	1	1.01	1.78
<i>Cullenia exarillata</i>	3.05	11.59	3	2.21	3	3.03	16.82
<i>Myristica dactiloides</i>	0.57	2.18	3	2.21	3	3.03	7.41
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	4.33	16.44	14	10.29	9	9.09	35.83
<i>Clerodendron sp.</i>	0.05	0.20	5	3.68	3	3.03	6.90
<i>Mallotus tetracoccus</i>	0.01	0.04	1	0.74	1	1.01	1.78
<i>Dysolxylum malabaricum</i>	0.05	0.19	1	0.74	1	1.01	1.94
<i>Antidesma menesu</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Bhesa indica</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Cinnamomum sulphuratum</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Cryptocarya sp.</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Nothopegia racemosa</i>	0.07	0.26	1	0.70	1	1.01	1.97
<i>Toona ciliata</i>	0.86	3.25	3	2.21	3	3.03	8.49
<i>Persea macarantha</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	1.25	4.73	3	2.21	3	3.03	9.96
<i>Syzygium zeylanicum</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Grewelia robusta</i>	1.40	5.33	9	6.62	8	8.08	20.03
<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	0.79	2.99	2	1.47	2	2.02	6.49
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>	1.28	4.87	8	5.88	4	4.04	14.80
<i>Elaeocarpus serratus</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Trichelia connoroides</i>	0.08	0.30	1	0.74	1	1.01	2.05
<i>Erythrina sp.</i>	0.04	0.17	4	2.94	2	2.02	5.13
<i>Dalbergia sp.</i>	0.15	0.58	2	1.47	2	2.02	4.07
<i>Prunus zeylanicum</i>	0.06	0.23	1	0.68	1	1.01	1.92
Total	26.35	100	136	100	99	100	300

BA-Basal area; IVI-Importance value index

Formula for the calculation of IVI :

IVI = Relative dominance + Relative Density + Relative Frequency of a species

where,

$$\text{Relative Dominance} = \frac{\text{Basal area of a species}}{\text{Basal area of all species}} * 100$$

$$\text{Relative Density} = \frac{\text{Density of a species}}{\text{Density of all species}} * 100$$

$$\text{Relative frequency} = \frac{\text{Frequency of occurrence of a species in sampling plots}}{\text{No. of plots sampled}} * 100$$